

BABYLONIAN, GREEK, AND INDIAN ASTRONOMY
(INDIAN ASTRONOMY IN HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE)

BY

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My intention in this paper is to attempt to illustrate through the history of mathematical astronomy two propositions that are pertinent to the problem of western and non-western ethnocentrism. The first is that scientific theories are products of the cultures in which they are developed—that is, that the sciences—and one must include its modern western manifestation along with all the others—are not intellectual conceptualizations of objective reality, but are based on learned modes of responding to and understanding subjective perceptions of arbitrarily chosen phenomena, which may be real to one culture while unreal to another. It is the culture that decides the modes of responding, the characteristics that identify significant phenomena, and the purposes and goals of the scientific enterprise. The second proposition that I wish to illustrate is that historically the transfer of scientific theories from one culture to another has been a normal and necessary contributor to the development of the sciences in the various cultures of the world, but that each recipient culture has transformed the interpretations of phenomena that it has received so that they fit into the norms of its own intellectual traditions. Within the broader history of science there is a certain unity that springs from this constant transmission, but it coexists with a diversity produced

by the refraction of scientific ideas as they pass through the numerous local intellectual prisms.

Within this theoretical framework it is easy to perceive that what has happened in the last 150 years is that the west's earlier dream of the conversion of the external "barbarians" in need of our allegedly unique path of salvation, a dream rather unsuccessfully promoted by Christianity to the confusion and dismay of many non-Christians, has been replaced by the far more successful promotion of western science as the provider, not of the spiritual salvation promised by the church, but of the material prosperity made possible by technology. In this process the formerly despised non-believers have been transformed into the equally despised underdeveloped; and the political and intellectual leaders of those non-Christian and underdeveloped nations have accepted this western judgment of their scientific inferiority, being desirous of acquiring both the military and the commercial products of technology. To achieve the new goals imposed on their cultures by our successful blend of *δευξια* and *τεχνη* they must train scientists and ordinary citizens capable of operating in a western mode. The effect has been to destroy the vitality of the scientific traditions of every culture but our own, though in many areas popular manifestations of the former sciences persist, often mingled with absorbable aspects of western science or even spuriously defended as "scientific" not in terms of the local intellectual traditions, but in terms of those borrowed from the west. As historians we not only observe and try to understand this process; but also regret that the world's former diversity is being so drastically diminished. However, our task is definitely not to judge the ultimate truthfulness or falseness of any

scientific system; that question is irrelevant to history, though the usefulness of the science for the culture in which it thrives is very much a part of its history.

Now to turn to the history of mathematical astronomy through which I intend to explore these themes. Our contemporary colleagues, the archaeoastronomers, continuing a western tradition solidly rooted in the attitudes of such ancient and medieval historians of science as Aristotle and Aëtius, who grossly distorted the cosmological theories of the Pre-Socratics by "modernizing" them, and as Al-Bīrūnī, who could not grasp the non-Euclidean genius of Indian mathematicians and astronomers—these modern archaeoastronomers attempt to interpret megalithic monuments as encoding concepts of the periodicity of celestial phenomena on the assumptions that the peoples who built them somehow shared the modes of thought and the intellectual goals that western culture developed only millennia later, and that megalithic societies admired these alleged astronomical discoveries to such an extent that they moved, at enormous expense, tons of stone in order to construct physical analogues to the phenomena, analogues which were totally useless since memory can store the information assumed to be thus recorded, as also can much smaller physical analogues. It is the apotheosis of science and scientists in our culture that leads the archaeoastronomers to believe that science can answer questions of history with awesome accuracy, a belief that is proving to be terribly detrimental to a more traditional view of the nature of historical evidence and of the conclusions that can be legitimately drawn from it; a belief that substitutes simple computation for the complexity and arbitrariness of the workings of the human

mind, and that improperly imposes statistical analysis on historical events, that are each a set of one.

Once we discard such bizarre ideas as the one that the megalithic builders of Stonehenge and other monuments had somehow, without any relevant background known to us, made discoveries concealed from everyone else till modern times, we are left with the recorded facts. The earliest datable observations of solar, lunar, and planetary phenomena are those detailed in the great Akkadian celestial omen series, Enūma Anu Enlil; Tablet 63 of that text, for instance, records a series of the dates of the observations of the heliacal risings and settings of Venus during the reign of the Old Babylonian king, Ammišaduqa, in the early seventeenth century B.C. Though the several thousand cuneiform fragments of celestial omens related to Enūma Anu Enlil were copied overwhelmingly in the seventh and later centuries B.C., internal evidence and the existence of Hittite translations of some tablets made in the middle of the second millennium, ^{substantiate the theory that} during the period of the Old Babylonian Kingdom, a number of celestial phenomena were utilized in making predictions concerning what was destined to happen to the king, to his court, and to his country. These omens depended upon such phenomena as the appearance of the new moon and the full moon and of lunar and solar eclipses, as the moon's and the planets' passings by each other and through certain constellations; and upon certain horizon phenomena of the planets--for example, their heliacal risings and settings, that is, their first visibilities and first invisibilities on the eastern horizon before sunrise and on the western horizon after sunset. The Old Babylonian Bārus viewed many other celestial phenomena as transmitting messages from the gods to men learned in

the ways of interpreting them, but the phenomena I have named are the ones, since they are periodic, that could be potentially and eventually were in fact, predicted by mathematical models.

But before the observational astronomy of the Old Babylonian period could be transformed into mathematically predictive astronomy, it was necessary for the Babylonians to realize the periodicity of the sets of phenomena named above. The evidence all indicates that this discovery, with respect to at least some of the phenomena, was made in the last few centuries of the second millennium, in the Assyrian kingdom of northern Mesopotamia. There there were developed not only a simple model governing the periodic recurrence of the Venus horizon phenomena based on constant, mean periods, but also the application of a more sophisticated mathematical tool, the zig-zag function, to deal with the deviations from the mean inherent in reality. In a zig-zag function one sets a maximum and a minimum value equidistant from the mean, and allows the values of the function to increase from the minimum to the maximum in equal steps separated by equal intervals of time, and then to return from the maximum to the minimum in the same fashion. In the earliest occurrences, which deal with a derivative of the length of daylight during a solar year and with the duration of moonlight during a mean synodic month, the period--a solar year and a mean synodic month respectively--contains an integer number of steps; and a modern graphical representation of such a zig-zag function would show for each period, a straight line sloping from the minimum to the maximum connecting to another straight line sloping at the same angle from the maximum to the minimum. The coordinates of each position on these lines are

determined by the lapsed time from the beginning of the period, measured by the number of steps taken, and the sum of an equal number of positive and/or negative applications of the common difference to the minimum value. In other words, to compute the desired values mathematically one needs only to utilize the arithmetical operations of addition and subtraction; yet the result is a good approximation to whatever curve it is that in reality passes through the values appropriate to the phenomenon being predicted. I am speaking geometrically of lines and curves; that is how our culture most easily grasps the meaning of the columns of numbers that were actually written on the cuneiform tablets.

When, after many developments in both the science of celestial omens and in that of observational astronomy, the Babylonians, through the accumulation of recorded and dated observations of periodic phenomena over several centuries--this was in the fifth century B.C.--were looking for a mathematical model that would allow them to predict phenomena presenting far more complex patterns than the annually varying length of daylight or the monthly varying length of moonlight, they extended the linear zig-zag function to serve a new purpose. To accomplish this they utilized a practical realization that, for a phenomenon such as the heliacal rising or setting of a planet, or its first station or second station (that is, the beginning and the end of its retrogression), and for the three superior planets, their acronychal risings when they appear above the eastern horizon as the sun is setting in the west (these phenomena, meaningless to us, were defined by the culture as significant)--that each of these phenomena recurred at about the

same place with respect to the constellations and at determinable dates in a properly intercalated lunà-solar calendar, such as the Babylonian calendar had come to be in the early fifth century B.C., in certain intervals of time or periods. The periods in which these recurrences took place we call goal-year periods. They are relatively short--59 years for Saturn, 71 or 83 years for Jupiter, 79 years for Mars, 8 years for Venus, and 46 years for Mercury. Someone realized that, if one counted the number of occurrences of a phenomenon in a goal-year period and distributed them over the measuring stick, the twelve zodiacal signs (for this purpose the zodiac need not be a circle, but can be considered a straight line), then the period, P , defined as the number of equally spaced occurrences of the phenomenon that can fit into the measuring stick, is equal to the quotient of the total number of occurrences of the phenomenon in a goal-year, π , divided by the number of these π occurrences that intervene between two successive occurrences, $Z \leftarrow P = \pi/Z$.

Through simple manipulations of the goal-year periods one can form highly accurate long synodic periods--265 years for Saturn, 427 years for Jupiter, 284 years for Mars, 1151 years for Venus, and 480 years for Mercury--and the numbers π and Z appropriate for each. Moreover, by simply counting over a goal-year period (the astronomers presumably had access to the tablets on which such observations were recorded, the Diaries, and needed to make none of their own) the number of occurrences of a phenomenon in each zodiacal sign, one derived the distribution pattern of the varying intervals in time and longitude between successive occurrences, and could construct a linear zig-zag function which was controlled by the relation $P = \pi/Z$, but in which the maximum and the minimum values and common

difference could be selected for their ease of use in simple addition, subtraction, and division. Along with this new application of the old zig-zag function, the Babylonian astronomers devised a so-called step function that satisfied the same conditions. Synodic periods of varying lengths were distributed in relation to certain fixed stars by purely arithmetical means without the imposition of such geometrical concepts as an elliptical orbit--indeed, without the concept of an orbit at all.

What the Babylonians had achieved by the end of the fourth century B.C. was the ability to predict the times and longitudes of the occurrences of selected planetary phenomena with very high accuracy for naked-eye observations, and to predict the times of the first sighting of the new moon at Babylon as well as the times and magnitudes of lunar eclipses. It is impressive to realize that the problem of predicting lunar phenomena had been analyzed as depending on the determination of eighteen different variables. These extraordinary achievements depend on simple arithmetical procedures; there are no geometrical models, and there are no accurate observations. The procedure depended on the averaging out of many poor observations over a relatively short period, and projecting the system to cover much longer periods. The Babylonians had been fortunate that their omens drew their attention to phenomena that, in our cosmology, depend on the fact that they are observed from a particular place on the surface of the earth as it travels about the sun; the variable that needed to be accounted for by the linear zig-zag or the step function depends on the ellipticity of the planet's orbit about the sun, and they could ignore the effect of the earth's rotation about that luminary. By pure luck, then, the character of

the ominous phenomena eliminated the need to deal with more than one inequality in motion. Moreover, once the dates and longitudes of the occurrences of each phenomenon were determined, it was simple to devise mathematical means for bridging the gaps in time and space between two successive phenomena. So, by 300 B.C. Mesopotamia possessed the world's first mathematical means for predicting successfully the longitudes of the sun, the moon, and the planets at any given time. This ability served to ease the task of those employed to search for celestial omens, and it facilitated the development of means of applying celestial omens to the prediction of the lives of individuals through horoscopes cast for the times of conception and birth. Probably it also provided joy and satisfaction to the astronomer-mathematicians who discovered the methods; but of that joy of discovery the cuneiform tablets do not speak.

Some of the Babylonian discoveries concerning the constellations and the periodicity of some solar and lunar phenomena, as summarized in our oldest astronomical handbook, Mul.Apin, begin to appear simultaneously in Greece and in India in the first half of the last millennium B.C. Echoes of this borrowed knowledge are found in Homer's Iliad and Odyssey, in Hesiod's Works and Days, and, with respect to the turning points on the eastern and western horizons of the sun's rising and setting points, among the genuine accounts of the activities of Pherecydes of Syrus and of Thales of Miletus; largely different parts of Mul.Apin influenced in India the Sanskrit Atharvaveda and various Brāhmanas in which they were used to help govern the timing of the performances of Śrauta rituals.

While economically the Eurasian continent from the Mediterranean to the Panjab had enjoyed a varying degree of contact since at least the middle of the third millennium B.C., political unity was achieved only by the foundation of the Achaemenid empire in the latter half of the sixth century B.C. The first result of this political unification and of the consequent increased possibility of intellectual exchange was the appearance, in both Greece and India, of a cosmology in which the sun, the moon, and the stars are rotating about a northern mountain, the celestial bodies being carried by wheels parallel to the earth's flat surface. The Greek version of this flat-earth cosmology is attributed to Anaximander and to his student, Anaximenes; the Indian version is found in Buddhist and Jain writings and in the Purānas. The common source is probably Mesopotamian, filtered through Iranian intermediaries who added the solar, lunar, and stellar wheels. With this cosmology, meant to explain the phenomena of day and night but incapable of accounting for eclipses, either solar or lunar, the idea of the presence of circular motion in the sky was introduced to both the Greeks and the Indians, at the extreme edges of the Achaemenid empire.

But it was the Greeks, in the fifth century B.C., who, for theological reasons, or philosophical, mathematical, or aesthetic if one chooses to view them as such, first conceived of the universe as a sphere, because the divine, which is the all, and a sphere share the attribute of perfection in unity. The bias of western mathematical astronomy for geometrical models springs from this simple equation, which the far more advanced Babylonians never conceived of, and which Indian astronomers only adopted in the fifth century A.D. The Greeks, with Aristotle's theory of the

natural circular motion of the fifth element, the ether, thought of as the sole constituent of heavenly bodies, added a physical, mechanical force, which has no convincing observational or experimental basis, to the purely mathematical problem solved by the Babylonians of predicting celestial phenomena. This Aristotelian bias was not transmitted to India along with Greek geometrical models, so that the Indians developed a mathematics for astronomy that could be more imaginative than the Greek because it was not bound to obey arbitrary laws of mechanics; but the Arabs ended up taking Aristotle's physics as seriously as they did Ptolemy's mathematics, and thereby were led to devise the mathematical solutions to problems arising from the incompatibility of Greek physical and mathematical astronomy that anticipated by three hundred years the mathematical part of Copernicus' astronomy. Let me now flesh out that brief summary of the history of astronomy over some two full millennia.

It was to the late fifth century B.C. theories of cosmology devised by Pythagoreans such as Philolaos that Plato owed his conviction that geometry was the proper mathematical tool for describing the ideal noetic motions of the sun, the moon, and the planets, though he believed astronomy to be properly unconcerned with sense perceptions. However, it was the originally Babylonian discovery of the periodicity of those motions, already introduced into Athens by Meton, that led him to believe in the order and predictability of the ideal if not of the observed motions of the heavens. His pupil, Eudoxus, brilliantly conceived of a geometrical model of internested spheres rotating at different velocities on poles angled to and embedded in their surrounding spheres that would produce, at

least qualitatively, the major planetary phenomena of retrogression and latitude. He had, however, and could have no parameters for these models which would enable them to be used to predict the observed phenomena. And his master, Plato, would have emphatically agreed that the failure of theory to coincide with observed reality was advantageous rather than detrimental to his science.

Predictive geometrical models became possible only in the second century B.C., when Hipparchus obtained a knowledge of Babylonian period relations, with specific numbers. Since these numbers do not occur in nature, but are the product of arithmetical models peculiar to Mesopotamia, the idea of independent discovery can not be considered as possible. This is true of all mathematical models of natural phenomena; they are the products not of a general human ability to interpret nature in a unique way, but of the mathematical procedures developed in the culture that brings them forth. They serve, therefore, as tracer elements which allow us to follow the spread of the mathematicized sciences wherever they go. Hipparchus also introduced into astronomy a method of using carefully chosen and precisely made observations to confirm the hypothetical geometrical models and to refine their dimensions. Few were to follow him in this in antiquity.

While Hipparchus began the long process of converting the earlier Greek notion of the ideal spherical motions of the heavens into a geometrical model in a plane that, by a combination of circular motions, traced the observed path of a planet with fair accuracy, the culmination of the process was the system achieved by Ptolemy in about 150 A.D. Briefly, the Ptolemaic model hypothesizes an epicycle on which the planet rides while the epicycle's center revolves

about a deferent circle whose geometric center is away from the center of the earth, which is the center of the universe, and at a velocity governed by another point different from both the center of the earth and the geometric center of the deferent. This eccentric deferent and the non-uniform motion of the epicycle's center about its periphery with reasonable accuracy describe the elliptical orbit of the planet about the sun, while the rotation of the planet about the circumference of the epicycle nearly corresponds to the earth's annual rotation about the sun.

The anciently perceived difficulty with Ptolemy's model was, then, not that it was inaccurate and not that it was geocentric, but that it allowed for non-uniform, and therefore, for philosophers, non-real, motion on the circumference of a circle by placing the center of uniform motion at a point within the circle different from the geometrical center; that it was therefore impossible to construct a mechanical model of this cinematic model, so that the mathematics provided predictions but did not describe physical reality; and that the model for the moon brought that body regularly much closer to the earth than the variation in its apparent diameter indicated that it came. These were all physical rather than mathematical defects; and Muslim astronomers of the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries showed how mathematical models could be devised that removed these physical problems--which, it must be stressed, arose not from Ptolemy's theory of geocentricity, but from Aristotle's arbitrary laws of physics.

The Indians had received from Mesopotamia considerable knowledge about the periodicity of solar, lunar, and planetary motion, along with specific, tracer element parameters, when they accepted

and adapted to their own social needs Babylonian celestial and terrestrial omens in the fifth and fourth centuries B.C. Subsequent to this transmission the Babylonians had invented their full mathematical models, and substantial parts of those models had been transmitted to the Greeks, who combined their potential for predicting longitudes with elements of Aristotelian physics to produce the new science of astrology. This was done in Hellenistic Egypt, in the late second century B.C. Beginning in the late first century B.C., with Roman control of Egypt and the Red Sea, an enormous trade in spices, manufactured goods (including many varieties of cloth, ceramics, and metal products), pharmaceuticals, and raw materials of all kinds sprang up between western and southern India on the one hand and the Mediterranean on the other. Numerous colonists of the Greek-speaking population of what used to be the Hellenistic kingdoms went out to India; archaeologists in Gujarat, Mahārāṣṭra, Mysore, Kerala, Tamilnad, and Āndhrapradeśa have been uncovering the material remains of these Greek colonies for the last century and a half; the intellectual remains that have so far been positively identified lie in the mathematicized sciences, mainly astrology and astronomy.

The first Greek astrological text to be introduced into India was the Yavanajātaka of Yavaneśvara, translated into Sanskrit in 149 A.D. at Ujjayinī, which from that time on was considered to lie on the world's prime meridian by Indian astronomers, an idea that western European astronomers, as we shall see, shared with the Indians as well as with many Muslims in the twelfth, thirteenth, and fourteenth centuries. To practice astrology it is necessary to be able to compute planetary longitudes for any given time; what the

Yavanajātaka offered to fill this need was a truncated Greek adaptation of Babylonian planetary theory, such as is now being uncovered from the numerous Greek astronomical papyri from Egypt, not the contemporary geometrical astronomy of Ptolemy. In the following two centuries several more Greek adaptations of Babylonian theory intermingled with elements from Hellenistic models derived from Hipparchus--all identifiable by their tracer element mathematical structure and parameters--were introduced into India, and there modified in accordance with local traditions of the calendar and of the mathematics of linear zig-zag functions--both ultimately of Babylonian origin. In this way, in a sense, the historical sequence of events that had taken place in Mesopotamian astronomy between 500 and 300 B.C. was repeated in India between 400 B.C. and 300 A.D.; but on the Indian side new astronomical theories were not generated except through fusion of and with elements borrowed from outside of their culture.

Finally, in the early fifth century A.D., Greek geometrical models of celestial motions were transmitted to India. But they were not those of Ptolemy's Almagest; rather, they were devised to account for one of the problems posed to geometrical astronomy by Aristotelian physics, that of the concentric motion of the celestial spheres about the earth, which was thought to lie at the center of the κόσμος. Those who followed Hipparchus tended to sacrifice concentricity to uniformity of motion. These followers of Hipparchus would have included Ptolemy if he had not violated the principle of uniformity of motion as well with the equant. Others, traces of whose ideas can be found in surviving Greek works such as Theon of Smyrna's treatise On the Mathematics Needed to Read Plato, sacrificed uniformity of motion in order to retain its concentricity.

ity. This is true of the principle Greek geometrical model introduced into India. The mean planet moves uniformly on a circle concentric with the center of the earth, but the physical planet is pulled from its mean position at every instant by two forces corresponding to the eccentric deferent, i.e., elliptical orbit of the planet, and to its epicycle, i.e., the orbit of the earth. The effects of these forces can be computed by means of two epicycles whose common center is the physical planet. The ways in which the two effects are integrated provide the planet with a non-continuous, bumpy motion along its concentric deferent.

Though this theory was based on Aristotelian physics, that physics was not transmitted to India along with the models. Indian astronomers, then, naturally viewed these geometrical models as being simply mathematical devices for computing the answers to certain questions; the concentric deferent spheres they usually regarded as having a physical reality, but the epicycles, eccentrics, and other parts of the Greek geometrical models served no purpose other than to facilitate computation. Nor was the Hipparchan tradition of utilizing observations to refine both the models and their parameters transmitted to India. The result was to free the mathematical inventiveness of Indian astronomers from the constraints of either physical laws or observational "reality."

The computations based on the Greek physical models could obviously be improved over what the Greeks, who took them seriously, had been doing. So the Indians took Hipparchus' chords and invented sines, cosines, and versines, and a whole panoply of trigonometrical relationships, which, as transmitted to and developed by the Muslims,

form the basis of our modern trigonometry. Not having Menelaus' theorem for solving angles on the surface of a sphere, the Indians, again basing themselves on Hipparchus, developed to an extraordinary degree the application of analemmata to the solution of problems in spherics; these Indian analemmata, again transmitted to and developed by the Muslims, continued to play a role in Western dialling until the seventeenth century. For the full geometric solution of the triangles produced by epicycles and eccenters the Indians substituted, when the angles were sufficiently small, the imposition of a simple sine-wave, a technique they applied to other problems where it is necessary to describe a function that varies between zero and a known maximum. These techniques also came to be familiar in medieval Islam and Europe, though not the later Indian technique of bending the sine-wave to fit any desired curve. Finally, in this early phase, they adapted the Platonic idea of a great year, in which all the planets return to the same longitudes at its end that they had occupied at its beginning,--they adapted this Great Year to an older Indian chronological scheme, based on a Babylonian parameter, according to which the physical universe in which we live endures for a kalpa of 4,320,000,000 years. This adaptation meant that each celestial body was computed to rotate an integer number of times within a kalpa, all starting from Aries 0° , with the interval from the beginning of the kalpa to our time so chosen, together with the numbers of the planets' rotations, that their computed mean longitudes correspond more or less with their actual values. Without the Indians' having direct knowledge of either Plato or Aristotle, their planetary theory was profoundly influenced by both. Such ideas were developed in the sixth century, in

Sasanian Iran, into forms of historical astrology utilizing the periodic conjunctions of the planets at given longitudes to predict the fates of dynasties and of religions. These conceptions of historical astrology and their applications to contemporary events were still being debated in sixteenth century Europe by proponents of the Holy Roman Empire and of Catholicism against the proponents of the German princes and the Protestant Reformation.

The Indians, then, ignored the physical problem of inventing new geometrical models in an attempt to bridge the gaps between Ptolemy and Aristotle because, in fact, they knew neither the Almagest nor the De Caelo and Metaphysics. What they had received and adopted from the Greeks, when suitably improved to meet their criteria, was quite sufficient to satisfy their needs for horoscopes, calendars, and eclipse-predictions. But they applied their genius in mathematics to the solution of other problems. So they utilized the cosine-function to compute the instantaneous velocity of the moon and of any planet; they applied their solution of indeterminate equations to the reconstruction of the dates of partially preserved horoscopes; they brilliantly investigated the properties of cyclic quadrilaterals; and eventually, in about 1400--two and a half centuries before this was done in Europe--one of their most brilliant mathematicians, Mādhava of Saṅgamagrāma, discovered the infinite series for π and the infinite power series for the sine, cosine, and tangent functions. These and other mathematical feats were accomplished without axiomatic geometry, without a theory of proof.

When Islam overwhelmed the Near East and Middle East in the seventh century, the Arabs conquered peoples in Syria, in Mesopot-

omia, and in Iran who had already begun the process of amalgamating the astronomical traditions of Ptolemy and the Indians. This process was carried forward in Arabic in the late eighth and ninth centuries, with the Ptolemaic two-dimensional circles reconceived of as lying on hollow and solid material spheres, and with mathematical tools enhanced by the adaptation from the Indian side of trigonometry, of complex analemmata, and of algebraic approximate solutions. But Islamic scientists also embraced the philosophy of Aristotle, so that by the eleventh century men like Ibn Al-Haytham were severely criticizing Ptolemy, as had Proclus and others in late antiquity, for the fact that his geometrical models, while producing, when the parameters were suitably modified, correct longitudes and latitudes, failed to represent physical reality. Unlike Proclus, the Muslims had the mathematical tools, the imagination, and the motivation to devise new models that, to a large extent, obviated the discrepancies. The great breakthroughs in the development of these new models occurred first in Iran in the thirteenth century when Naṣīr al-Dīn al-Ṭūsī invented a coupling of circles that transformed circular into linear motion, allowing non-uniform motion to be replaced by philosophically correct motion. A number of other changes in the models introduced by Al-^{Urdī}, Quṭb al-Dīn al-Shīrāzī, and others, including himself, eventually allowed Ibn al-Shātīr of Damascus in the first half of the fourteenth century to utilize all of the mathematical solutions that, two centuries later, Copernicus incorporated into his De Revolutionibus.

We should briefly now turn to the history of western astronomy--and we can be very brief because very little happened of

fundamental importance. After Ptolemy the Greeks made no serious contributions to mathematical astronomy--which, indeed, relatively few in Byzantium between the sixth and the fourteenth centuries managed to understand to any extent beyond what was sufficient to cast a horoscope. In the west the situation was even more desolate. The sixth century attempt to translate Ptolemy's Handy Tables into Latin was a disaster; it did not even allow astrologers to practice their science, which died in western Europe not because of its intellectual inadequacy, but because of the intellectual inadequacy of the western Europeans. They gained the long sought ability to practice astrology not with the multiple translations of the Almagest in the twelfth century; for, in fact, despite the existence of about a hundred medieval manuscripts of these translations, no medieval western astronomer was able to demonstrate that he understood the text. That was achieved in Europe only in the late fifteenth century, by Peurbach and Regiomontanus. Rather, it was the translation of Arabic adaptations of Indian astronomical tables, such as that of Al-Zīj al-Sindhī of Al-Khwārizmī by Adelard of Bath in 1126, that enabled scientists of the Latin tradition for the first time to compute and predict planetary phenomena. In the twelfth, thirteenth, and fourteenth centuries, western European astronomers did little beyond absorbing at a rather low level the Indian and Islamic material made available to them in the cultural back-water that was Andalusia; their main achievement was in the design and construction of astronomical instruments. In astronomy, at least, the west was the most primitive culture in Eurasia, far outstripped by the Indians and the Muslim and Jewish inhabitants of the Near and Middle East and of North Africa, all of whom were heirs to the Babylonian, the Greek, and the

scientific traditions.

Within this historical framework, the developments in mathematical positional astronomy of the last half millennium in the west represent merely the most recent reworkings of this Babylonian, Greek, Indian, and Islamic heritage. The modern science's methods and its assumptions have been determined by history and by a variety of cultural attitudes and experiences to which it has been heir; they do not arise directly from nature itself. The content of this science also, then, since, while it originates to some extent in the application in imaginative ways of these methods and assumptions to sense perceptions, yet to a far larger extent depends on the creation of speculative mathematical models, is a product of culture just as were also the astronomies of the other cultures we have briefly examined. Copernicus, Kepler, and Newton made but the latest attempts to resolve the Greco-Muslim difficulty of reconciling mathematical with physical astronomy. This is especially true of Copernicus, who may be regarded in many respects as the last of the medieval Muslim astronomers. As was true of them, his trigonometry was Indian, his parameters were modified Ptolemaic, and his planetary models were Middle Eastern. All that he did differently was inconsistently to throw out the Aristotelian physics that the Muslim mathematical models that he adopted were designed to accommodate. This strange behavior left a glaring lacuna in western astronomical theory that it took over a century to bridge. No other culture than that of sixteenth and seventeenth western Europe, we may be confident, could have achieved Newton's great system; but, due to that system's, and our culture's, unparal-

leled success, there no longer survive any non-western scientific traditions to fertilize ours with different perspectives. One cannot imagine easily what Babylonian, Byzantine, Indian, or Islamic astronomies might have evolved into had they and their cultures not succumbed, though we can be sure that they would be different sciences from that now taught in our universities.